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PRAGUE 2024

**XV International
Palynological Congress
XI International Organization
of Palaeobotany Conference**

**27–31 May 2024, Prague
Czech Republic**

**Abstract
Book**

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ABSTRACT BOOK

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pollen florulas. Each local flora obtained this way was then uploaded to PROTO Database, which allows for searching plants by location, by chronology, by pollen type/group and by species.

28/05/2024, 17:00–18:40, Room: Virgo

Z04 Palynology and palaeobotany in the digital era

O-093 - Exploring human-plant interactions in central Italy over the centuries: Compiling and comparing published and unpublished archaeobotanical records

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The gradual implementation of archaeobotany in archaeological excavations in the Italian territory in last decades has greatly helped to gain knowledge about past human-plant interactions. Information is now available, among others, about diet, selection of natural resources, introduced taxa, and ritual uses of plants. However, archaeobotanical studies continue to be published in different types of sources, such as scientific articles and archaeological reports, the latter of which are often complex to retrieve. Furthermore, data often concern single contexts or sites, making it hard to piece the puzzle together.

A noteworthy step to obtain an overall picture of human plant interactions in Italy is represented, since 2015, by BRAIN (Botanical Record of Archaeobotany Italian Network), a cooperative network and database listing all the sites, their locations, chronology, cultures, archaeological contexts, and various types of archaeobotanical studies conducted, along with their bibliographic references. The database is periodically updated with new publications.

In this study, produced within the PNRR PE5 CHANGES Spoke 8 and CN5 NBFC Spoke 3, we present a georeferenced tool to compare data about plant macro-remains extracted from publications present in BRAIN and deriving from unpublished studies, homogenizing them, and sorting them by periods. The project now covers central Italy and will gradually be implemented to include the rest of the country. Through the implementation of the developed protocol, the reconstruction of dietary preferences and the introduction of new plants from the Neolithic to the modern-day will be more accessible and straightforward. It will thus be possible, for example, to better trace the arrival and spread of archaeophytes and neophytes in the Italian Peninsula.

28/05/2024, 17:00–18:40, Room: Virgo

Z04 Palynology and palaeobotany in the digital era

O-094 - Using convolutional neural networks to predict the phylogenetic and ecological affinities of fossil moss spores

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Mosses play a critical role in key biomes such as boglands, tundra, and temperate rainforests. However, their sparse fossil record limits our understanding of their role in past ecosystems. Additionally, mosses occupy an essential phylogenetic position, yet there are few fossils to provide useful minimum age nodes for phylogenetic analyses. Fossil spores offer the potential to address these limitations given their significantly greater chance of being preserved in the fossil record. Except for *Sphagnum*, few moss spores are recorded in deep time, likely because of their frequently smaller size and lack of easily visible diagnostic features typically used in spore identification. Here, we have developed Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for the first time in mosses using SEM images of extant moss spores to predict the phylogenetic and/or ecological affinities of fossil moss spores. CNNs learn features directly from image data for classification tasks, without requiring manual feature selection. To develop this CNN, we sampled over 200 moss species covering the breadth of the moss phylogeny. Lycophytes and ferns were also sampled to use as outgroups. SEM imaging allows for the surface perine sculpturing of mosses to be considered in the neural network, in contrast to light microscopy, where these features are not easily visible. While CNNs have previously been used on 3D scans of pollen, this is the first application

